

Document Change Log:

Version	Date	Author name(s)	Description of Change
1	2024-29-04	M. Brandić Lipińska	First version

Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
LUWEX	Lunar Water Extraction and Purification Technologies		
AI	Artificial Intelligence		
CE	Concurrent Engineering		
ISRU	In-Situ Resource Utilisation		

1 VIDEOCAST MINISERIES

A videocast mini-series brings to the foreground the people working on the project including the laboratory facilities with the LUWEX hardware and set-ups.

It is structured around small interviews with team members, where team members are answering questions about the LUWEX project (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Screenshots from the video miniseries

1.1 Episodes

There are five episodes in the series:

1. About LUWEX.

An interview with Paul Zabel, LUWEX project coordinator.

<https://luwex.space/2023/11/08/about-luwex/>

2. Motivation for LUWEX

What the project team inspires about project LUWEX.

<https://luwex.space/2023/11/07/motivation-for-luwex/>

3. About In-Situ-Resource-Utilisation ISRU

ISRU and how it is a sustainable practice.

<https://luwex.space/2023/11/06/about-in-situ-resource-utilisation-isru/>

4. LUWEX challenges

What kind of challenges the LUWEX team faces in developing the project.

<https://luwex.space/2023/11/05/luwex-challenges/>

5. LUWEX interviews on collaboration

Collaborative aspects of industry, academia and research institutions of project LUWEX.

<https://luwex.space/2023/11/04/luwex-interviews-on-collaboration/>

1.2 Presentation

The videocast miniseries is hosted on the LUWEX website (see Figure 2 and 3) and published on the partners YouTube channels (see Figure 4).

The episodes will also be shared via LUWEX LinkedIn profile.

Figure 2: Screenshot from the website video page, showcasing all the videocast miniseries episodes.

Figure 3: Screenshot from the website, from the separate video page.

Figure 3: Screenshot of the videocast episode published on YouTube.